

Student Absenteeism in Tertiary Education in Bangladesh: Causes and Effects

Md Mizanur Rahman¹ and Md. Habibullah Bahar²

¹*Deputy Secretary, Information and Communication Technology Division, Bangladesh, E-mail: rahmanboku@gmail.com

² Deputy Secretary, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh

*Correspondence: rahmanboku@gmail.com

Abstract

Tertiary education plays a very important role in the life of a student to become a learned man and to get a good job in future to have a secure life. But student absenteeism causes in a very significant way, the low quality of the students and ultimately poor passing rate in the examination. To find out the causes of student absenteeism at the tertiary level. Sirajganj Government College was selected for collecting data on student absenteeism in tertiary education. Data were collected both from primary and secondary sources. Four categories of respondents: Principals, Teachers, Students and Guardians were sampled during the study period. The study showed that absenteeism occurred due to poverty, distance from home to college, teachers' sympathy towards the students in all their examinations, bad road conditions, lack of accommodation, lack of security for female students, no support from in-laws house, physical illness, unattractive class teaching, involvement with politics, lack of co-curricular activities, dependence much on hand notes, guide books, and private tuition. Several measures such as regular counselling of students, the exercise of regular co-curricular activities, regular rollcall, and imposition of rules and regulations of National University can easily stop student absenteeism in tertiary education in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Student absenteeism, Tertiary Education, Bangladesh, Curricular, Poverty, Guide books

List of Abbreviations

ACAD	:	Advanced Course on Administration and Development
BANBEIS	:	Bangladesh Bureau of Educational Information & Statistics
Govt.	:	Government
Hon's	:	Honours
MDS	:	Member of Directing Staff
NP	:	Number of Principal
NG	:	Number of Guardian
MA	:	Master of Arts
NT	:	Number of Teachers
NS	:	Number of Students
NU	:	National University
SL. No	:	Serial Number
TTTM	:	Teacher Talking too much

1.0 Introduction

The Bangladesh Government aims to make all-round development in the country, especially by promoting the education system. So the Government is always ready to incur huge expenditures in the education system. Despite the highest budgetary allocation over the last decades in the education centre, we come to know from different studies that the output of the system is not satisfactory both in respect of quality and quantity. It is noticed that student absenteeism in tertiary education is increasing day by day. Policymakers, education specialists, administrators, teachers, and guardians are worried about their problem and they are suggesting ways to reduce absenteeism in tertiary education. To achieve SDGs in Bangladesh the education system warrants massive improvements (Rahman 2021; Rahman *et al.* 2020). The problem of student absenteeism stands in the way of the development of the country. So finding a realistic solution to this problem is the burning question nowadays.

1.1 Problem Statement

Tertiary education plays a very important role in the life of a student to become a learned man and to get a good job in future to have a better life. However, some surveys revealed that student absenteeism caused in a very significant way, the low quality of the students and ultimately poor passing rates in the examination. Therefore, considering the high stakes, student absenteeism deserves maximum attention. Since there is no systematic study on this issue. So it needs a proper study to find out the causes of absenteeism.

1.2 Objectives

The specific objectives of the research work are as follows:

- ✓ to know the current status of absenteeism at the tertiary level;

✓ to find out the causes of student absenteeism at the tertiary level

1.3 Scope

The study investigated the problem of student absenteeism. It also helped to find out the solutions to this severe problem remaining in the educational institutions. Therefore, the title of the study was selected as the cause of student absenteeism in tertiary education at the National University. A case study from Sirajganj Govt. College was taken here as a sample which reflects the real condition of tertiary education in our educational institutions. This study revealed why the students remained absent from the classrooms and how this problem could be solved. In this way, we can assume a clear idea about the condition of tertiary education in the educational institutions of Bangladesh.

1.4 Rationale of the Study

In our country, tertiary education is provided in public universities, private universities and Govt.-Non-govt. colleges under the National University. Sirajganj is one of the highly educated districts in Rajshahi division. She has a long record of having old educational institutes. She is trying her best to provide tertiary education for the young generation like all other districts of Bangladesh. My study on the above-mentioned topic is interesting for several reasons. A few of them are as follows:

This college is very ancient in providing tertiary education. Specially, Sirajganj Govt. College is one of the largest colleges in Bangladesh containing more than 18,000 students in this level.

This educational institution does not afford to provide proper class accommodation for the students. So, they are suffering from various crises related to quality education.

Among the students, the biggest portion is female students. Female students coming from remote places far from this city are highly affected by the crisis of accommodation, especially the residential crisis.

Socio-economic condition is also a vital reason behind the suffering of the students every year. If we succeed in solving the above-mentioned problems as soon as possible, tertiary education in Sirajganj district will be fruitful as well as the whole country will be benefitted. That is why, I have chosen this topic and this institute for my study.

2. Literature Review

Student absenteeism has already been identified by scholars of our country as a major problem prevailing in the tertiary educational institutions of Bangladesh. Many articles, reports and news have been published in newspapers and journals. Still, it demands more attention from all corners both of public and government to eradicate this problem immediately to ensure a bright future for our young generation. Keeping this viewpoint in mind, we need a lot of research work on this topic to spread consciousness among the people.

Review of related literature is an essential part of a research work. It gives researchers good background information about the concerned area of the research field, which helps to identify a research programme and conduct research smoothly. The literature review also helps to develop a methodology in which the method would be selected for the research work. With this view, researchers tried to look for related literature in different reliable sources and make a critical review. Necessary literature has been reviewed in this regard and cited here to some extent.

Bari, M.A (2001) in his studies on education-related problems pointed out that appropriate guidance, counselling, training and other forms of logistic support will make the students regular in the classroom.

Islam, T. (1997) mentioned that children are unhappy with their family problems over the years. Eventually, they do not come to their institutions regularly; even they stop to come to school.

Imtehas, A. (1993) noted that students avoid the class to carry out their parent's orders as workers to help the family issues where commercial interests are involved. Furthermore, when learners fail once to understand and are enjoyable.

Rahman, S. (1991) reported that teachers are usually very reluctant to teach hard chapters and newly included modules. As a result, learners used to go to private tutors and avoid going to colleges. Besides, they make the lessons as copies and enter the examination hall.

Rahman, S. Z. (1997) pointed out, in his article on Education for Development, that about 630 million people are extremely poor in Bangladesh. So most of the students remain absent from the class due to poverty.

Sharif, Y. (2000) highlighted that students usually boycott the classroom to project them as political leaders and workers. And this is the way they tend to demand undue privilege from the institution. Sometimes they avoid classes on; a lea of meagre issues thereby deadlocking the institutions.

Siddique, A. A. M.S. A. (1987) has pointed out in his writing on the title " The stigma of illiteracy" that rural students cannot afford to attend schools mainly for economic constraints. The period they spend in college does not bring them immediate monetary reward but if they work during the college hour they can either earn money or a meal.

Siraji, M.A. S. (2001) mentioned students do not go to educational institutions due to the failure of the teachers. He also added that teachers are not trained to keep the learner in the classroom by effectively delivering the lesson.

Longhurst (1999) noted that absenteeism resulted in poor learning for those absent, and disrupted classes for those who remained. The issue is seen to have practically applicable results and educational importance. A study on attendance at a college showed that 22% of students had missed classes at some point in time because of students work commitments. However, it was also accrued from the study that students' attendance in the classroom could be ensured by the incentives/punishments method. The main incentive/punishment open to lecturers is via the

assessment process (if that would be wonderful) if students interpreted the withdrawal of self-development opportunities as a serious punishment, but sadly, this is not always the case and so staff may need to consider incorporating some form of attendance assessment into students' course marks.

Pallas (1999) mentioned that poverty-poor children are more likely to perform poorly in school and to drop out than children from higher-income households. Young people are at risk, or educationally disadvantaged if they have been exposed to inadequate or inappropriate educational experiences in the family, school or community.

Kelly (1993) stated that it is generally acknowledged that extrinsic motivation is linked with increased performance whereas intrinsic motivation is related to positive attitudes towards work, low absenteeism, and low staff turnover.

Hackman and Oldham (1980) pointed out that the application of the carrot and stick policy in Higher Education might be that students win prizes for good performance and that the achievement of higher grades in examinations is a reward for increased effort.

Elton (1996) suggests that issues of lecturer presentation can be seen as influential functional approaches to learning in determining whether a student adopts a deep approach. Similarly, students' extrinsic motivation may be more important when the topic is disliked, when there is pressure to succeed when losing face amongst peers is important and when any learning is driven solely by the assessment of the course.

3. Methods and Materials

3.1 Data Collection

The study area of this study was Siraganj Govt. The college situated in the heart of the city plays a vital role in this field.

Most of the data required to answer and validate the research questions were collected from primary sources. Different methodology approaches such as questionnaires, focus group discussions and field observation were adopted. Data were collected not only from the students but also from the teachers. Moreover, the Principal and the guardians also helped in collecting the data. Secondary data were collected from some published books or journals.

3.2 Sample Size

Siraganj Govt. College was selected for collecting data on student absenteeism in tertiary education. Four categories of respondents, that is, Principals, teachers, students and guardians were sampled during the study period. At least, 148 students, 20 teachers, 10 guardians and the Principal of Siraganj Govt. Colleges were included in the sample. All the respondents were interviewed through random selection from Siraganj Govt. College.

3.3 Data Collection and Analysis

The selected college (Sirajganj Govt. College) was informed earlier and questionnaires were distributed among the respondents. It was made clear where queries arose and they made their comments in writing where necessary accordingly. The information about students' attendance, performances in public, and annual and test examinations were collected from the college register. Other information, socio-economic in particular, was collected through direct interviews. Relevant data were processed and transformed mostly with the help of the internet and computer software.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Results

A. Respondent Group: Principal

According to the Principal of Sirajganj Govt. College, 20 posts out of 106 are still vacant. The Principal was trying hard to continue all the classes to keep the normal programs of the college.

Academic Situation and Students' Performances

Students' enrolment, number of examinees appearing at the honours and Masters Examinations and rate of passing the examinations were increasing day by day. A decreasing trend was found among the students who were absentees. All these are presented graphically below:

Causes of Student Absenteeism

According to the Principal, there were many causes of student absenteeism. The main cause of student absenteeism was poverty. (50%) students at the tertiary level were compelled to find jobs and maintain his/her family expenses. Because of poverty, they were engaged in any kind of job to earn money and as a result, they gradually became absentees. Besides poverty, other factors were also involved in student absenteeism. Lack of accountability both from the teachers and the students was responsible for student absenteeism. Inefficient teachers are also responsible for it (6%). Classroom teaching is not understandable (4%). Late starting of class (3%), lack of good communication (3%), physical illness (5%), family reasons (2%), preferring to gossip with friends (3%), involvement with politics and showing power for it (5%), assumption of the students that it is better to read at home and private tutors (5%), local grouping (1%), lack of infrastructure facilities (1.5%), syllabus not completed in the class (7%), lack of co-curricular activities (1%) etc are the factors which are responsible for student absenteeism.

Strategies to be adopted to ensure the regularity of students

According to the Principal, different strict measures should be adopted to ensure the regularity of students. At first, both the students and the guardians should be informed at the higher secondary level. But at the tertiary level huge students in the college. Sometimes they have tried to Reduce

tutorial/in-course marks, and attendance marks, and impose the absentee students. Even the absentees should be awarded less marks in viva voce. If all the conditions and factors mentioned above are maintained strictly, but could not success to the absentee student in the tertiary education. Finally, absentee students get the opportunity to fill up the form for the examination.

Probable factors influencing dissatisfactory results in tertiary education

The Principal thinks that there are many factors which influence dissatisfactory results in tertiary education. The first factor is that nowadays many students do not want to work hard and they depend on cheap guidebooks and hand notes. Besides this, other factors such as unattractive sessions, irregular class conduction, irregular attendance, no good hand notes, lack of reading textbook, fewer standard questions, question leakage, repetition of questions, no completion of syllabus etc are influencing dissatisfactory results in the tertiary educations.

Effect of Absenteeism on student's future

The effect of absenteeism on student's future beggars description. The absentees cannot become good citizens. Their subject knowledge will always remain incomplete. They will have to be frustrated throughout their life.

B. Respondent Group: Teachers

Teaching experiences of classroom teachers

A total of 20 teachers have been interviewed. An overwhelming majority of the teachers (50%) have service experience of 5-10 years followed by 35% who have 10-15 years of experience while 25% of teachers have experience of 16-25 years.

Measures to be taken to ensure the maximum presence

In response to the measures to be taken to ensure the maximum presence, teachers have given their opinions which have been delineated in Table 1. The highest respondents (50%) opined that counselling the students with fellow teachers and guardians will be the best way to keep the students away from absenteeism. Other respondents (30%) opined that the imposition of strict rules and regulations of tertiary education could prevent the tendency of absenteeism. Other teachers argued that attractive and standard ways of teaching could stop absenteeism.

Measures to Make the Teaching-learning Process Enjoyable

In response to the open-ended questions on how to make the teaching and learning process enjoyable, teachers have given some significant suggestions. Most of the students suggest that in the lesson plan, there must be amusements. Students must not feel bored in the classroom. Rather they will enjoy the lessons or the lectures delivered by the teachers. Teachers must invent new ways which can draw the attention of all the students. In the classroom, teachers must not follow the T.T.T.M method, that is, the teacher talking too much. Students must be allowed to express their feelings and ideas. Teachers must arrange debate competitions so that all the students can

be encouraged. Some teachers opined that scholarships should be given to meritorious, regular and poor students. Diversity in teaching methods can prevent student absenteeism in tertiary education.

Causes of Student Absenteeism by Opinion of Teachers :

50% of teachers have identified that poverty and physical illness are the main causes of student absenteeism. 30% of teachers think that the lack of accountability of the students is the reason for students' absenteeism. Some teachers think that involvement with politics is also the reason for student absenteeism. Besides these, neglecting studies, gossiping with friends, and too much depending on private tutors and cheap guidebooks are further responsible for student absenteeism.

Table 1. *Opinions of the teachers in ensuring the maximum presence of students in the classroom (n=20)*

S1		No.	(%)
01	Suggestions to be taken to keep the students in the class		
	Counselling the students, conferring with fellow teachers and guardians	14	70%
02	Arranging scholarships for poor students	02	10%
03	Reward for regular student	8	40%
04	Deterring irregular students from appearing final exam	8	40%
05	Turning the classroom lively	9	45%
06	Enforcing regular attendance through fine and stringent rules	7	35%
07	Ensuring the accountability of the teachers to job assignments	6	30%
08	Bringing rationalization and novelty in question setting	2	10%
09	Controlling student's campus politics	5	25%
10	Transportation facilities for the students	1	5%
11	Inquiring about the weal and woe of students	4	20%
12	Initiative to bar private coaching	3	15%
13	Weekly refreshment class	2	10%
14	Banning notebooks in the market	2	10%
15	Appointment of meritorious teachers and train them properly	3	15%
16	Employment opportunities after completion of education	8	40%
17	Mandatory stipend for male students like female ones	2	10%
18	Enforcement of collegiate and non-collegiate system	7	35%
19	Teachers evaluation by the learners	8	40%
20	Eradicate unfairness from the exam system	2	10%
21	Banning coaching centers	8	40%
22	Clean and hygienic campus and classroom	12	60%
23	Pedagogy in 'reading for pleasure' format	3	15%
24	Training of Teachers in education psychology	1	5%
25	Students, parents, and teachers' days be arranged annually	2	10%
26	The adverse effect of absenteeism be explained to learners	2	10%

Effects of Absenteeism on the Future of Learners

Absenteeism creates an adverse effect on the future of the learners. An absentee can never be a good citizen. His subject knowledge becomes incomplete. In future, an absentee can neither be a good learner nor a good performer. A kind of frustration always haunts him throughout his life. He can't find a good job. In the competitive job market, he always lags.

Table 2: Measures taken to make the Teaching hearing process enjoyable to ensure the regular in the class. (NT=20)

S1	Opinions of teachers	No.	(%)
01	Programmes for amusement	16	80%
02	Arrangement of debate	11	55%
03	Arrangement of an educational excursion trip	18	90%
04	Keeping good books in the library	14	70%
05	Good counseling	16	80%
06	Question-answer session after each class	11	55%
07	Introduction of the audio-video system in the classroom	17	85%
08	Demonstration of theoretical discourses with the help of practical instruments	05	25%
09	Feed back system	16	80%
10	Co-curricular activities be in place	17	85%
11	Prize for a good result	12	60%
12	Through discussion method Interlocution	05	25%
13	Teaching method diversification	02	10%
14	The creativity of teachers be rekindled by offering research projects	10	20%
15	Scholarships for regular, poor, and meritorious students	11	55%

C. Respondent Group: Students

Register maintenance in the classroom to ensure regularity

The majority of the students (95%) mentioned that regular roll call was done in the classroom, whereas, only 5% reported that no roll call was done in the classroom. Furthermore, 80% of students were satisfied with the classroom presence while 20% were not.

Table 3: Register maintenance in the classroom

Regular roll call		Satisfactory student's presence	
Yes	No	Yes	No
95%	5%	80%	20%

Purified or disciplinary measures taken against the absentee students

The present study shows that an absenteeism problem existed (35%) in the institution and the

institution used to adopt different measures against the absentee students. Among the measures, 50% of students informed that guardians or the students were informed about absenteeism through the telephone. 25% of students informed that notices were insured to the guardians. 20% of students informed that institutions imposed fines on absentee students. Besides, show cause notices were served according to 5% of students.

Strategies to achieve better results without maintaining regularity in the classroom

The majority of the students (70%) expressed a general expectation of good results without maintaining regularity in the classroom while only 30%, replied negatively. 20% of students replied that good suggestions and handbooks are another way of doing well in the examination. 30% of students informed that it is possible to maximize time by avoiding classes and thereby utilize them for better study. 50% of students opined that being absent, no student can do well in the examination.

Probable causes of student absenteeism opined by students

In response to questions on causes of absenteeism, 30% of students identified that economic problem was the main reason for absenteeism from the class followed by 25% who argued that lack of accommodation was the cause of absenteeism. Distance from home to college is one of the reasons for absenteeism opined by 20% of Students. 10% of students identified that unattractive classroom teaching is also the cause of absenteeism. 10% of students think that they can do well in the examination by following the guidebooks. Only 5% argued that it is better to read at home rather than attend boring classes in college.

Table 4. Causes of student absenteeism by opinion of students (NS=148)

Sl. No	Causes of student absenteeism	Student	
		Yes	%
01	Classroom teaching is not understandable	23	15.54 %
02	Classroom teaching is not attractive	25	16.89%
03	Late starting of classes	11	7.43 %
04	In-efficient teachers	21	14.19%
05	Help their parents in household work	40	27.03 %
06	disturbed by a pervert on the way	5	3.38%
07	Lack of good communication	60	40.54%
08	Family reasons	80	54.05%
09	The assumption by students that it is better to read at home rather than attend classes in college	43	29.05%
10	Prefer to gossip with their friends	35	23.64%
11	Earning money for insolvency	54	36.49%
12	Involvement in student politics	45	30.41%
13	Conveyance costly	56	37.84%
14	Physical illness	10	6.76 %
15	Family members getting unwell	45	30.41%

16	Lack of residential facilities	42	28.38%
17	The syllabus was not completed in class	24	16.22%
18	Teachers don't give notes in class	53	35.81%
19	Lack of co-curricular activities	30	20.27 %

Subjects chosen for private tuition and schedule of it

The subjects which the students were compelled to undergo private tuition had been investigated. It was found that 80% of students selected English as a difficult subject as it is a compulsory subject in Tertiary education. Students also choose Mathematics, Accounting, Management, Physics, Chemistry, Zoology, Economics, and Statistics for private tuition. Most of the students choose either the morning or afternoon to get a convenient time for private tuition. On the other hand, students of English, Mathematics, Accounting, Physics and chemistry take private tuition as their source of income. Because of their private tuition, many students often remain absent from their classes.

Effects of absenteeism on the students

Most of the students show great anxiety about the effects of absenteeism in their future lives. Many of them fear that they will not be successful in future. Their subject knowledge will always remain incomplete. They think that they will lose the important time of their academic time which they will never cover. Because of absenteeism, they will always lack confidence. Few students think that frustration will haunt them throughout the rest of their lives.

D. Respondent Group: Guardians

In response to the structured questions, guardians of different professions of agriculture, business, teaching, Govt. service gave their clear opinions about student absenteeism in tertiary education under the National University. According to them, absenteeism hurts the students. According to the guardians, the main cause of absenteeism is the poverty. Many students have to run their families and manage the expenses of education not only for them but also for their brothers and sisters. They also think that physical illness is also the cause of absenteeism. Distance from home to college, lack of accommodation, lack of security for female students, bad road conciliation, participation in family activities, and irregular and low standard teaching in the honours level classes are also responsible for absenteeism in tertiary education.

Guardians' views about students' reliance on private tuition and coaching centre

50% of guardians believe that at the honours level, very few teachers are dutiful. Taking an insufficient number of classes, teachers cannot cover the syllabus. As a result, students depend more on private tuition than on class learning. In private tuition, they get selective teaching of important questions. Many guardians believe that it is somehow possible for a student to do well in the examination without attending the classes.

Probable Influence of absenteeism on students' career

The guardians put forward their valuable opinions about the influence of absenteeism on

students' careers. All the guardians spontaneously admitted that the knowledge of the absentees will never be complete. Many guardians fear that they will never be good citizens. Some guardians opined that as they have incomplete knowledge, they will never be able to compete for good jobs. The absentees will lack confidence.

Table 5: Effects of absenteeism overall future career of the student's opinion by respondents

Sl. No.	Assumed impediments	Completely agreed		Students (NS=148)	Guardians (NG=10)
		Principal (NP=01)	Classroom Teachers (NT=20)		
01	Can't grow as a good citizen	01 (100%)	15 (75%)	70 (47.3%)	7 (70%)
02	Can't grow as a good citizen	01 (100%)	12 (60%)	60 (40.55%)	6 (60%)
03	Wouldn't not law abiding citizen	01 (100%)	15 (75%)	70 (47.3%)	7 (70%)
04	Wouldn't be unsuccessful in future studies	01 (100%)	16 (80%)	75 (50.68%)	6 (60%)
05	Incomplete subject knowledge	01 (100%)	15 (75%)	80 (54.05%)	8 (80%)
06	The final stages of studies wouldn't be good	01 (100%)	12 (60%)	60 (40.54%)	9 (90%)
07	Higher studies difficult	01 (100%)	14 (70%)	50 (33.78%)	6 (60%)
08	Leads to the wrong path easily	No comment	16 (80%)	30 (20.27%)	5 (50%)
09	Sense of social values does not grow	01 (100%)	17 (85%)	40 (20.03%)	7(70%)
10	Don't develop proper personality	01 (100%)	15 (75%)	50 (33.78%)	6 (60%)

The absenteeism problem in tertiary education affects the student's overall performance both in their academic development and in their future career. The study reveals interesting findings that come out from the opinions of the respondent groups.

Causes of Student Absenteeism

Most of the respondents have pointed out that poverty is the main cause of student absenteeism followed by physical illness, Lack of accountability from any corner of teachers, administration, students and guardians has been identified as the root cause of student absenteeism. Depending on private tuition, availability of guidebooks, involvement with politics, lack of accommodation, distance from home to college, gossiping with friends during class time, lack of interaction among students and teachers, unattractive class teaching, inefficient teachers, lack of a requisite number of classrooms, helping family members by earning money have been identified as the

causes of student absenteeism. These findings are in good agreement with the result of the present study.

Table -6: Attendance collected from the register of different departments of Sirajganj Govt. College.

(a) 1st Year Hon's (Session-2010-11)

Subject	Total	Present	(%)	Absent	(%)
History	120	64	53.33%	56	46.67%
Physics	146	75	51.37%	71	48.63%
Political science	122	62	50.82%	60	49.18%
Philosophy	174	143	82.18%	31	17.82%
Islamic History	200	180	90.00%	20	10.00%
Management	46	35	76.09%	11	23.91%
Bangla	276	95	34.42%	181	65.58%
	1084	654	60.03%	249	22.97%

(b) 2nd YEAR Hon's (Session-2011-12)

subject	Total	Present	(%)	Absent	(%)
History	110	40	36.36%	70	63.64%
Physics	26	23	88.46%	03	11.54%
Political science	191	125	65.45%	66	34.55%
Philosophy	135	95	70.37%	40	29.63%
Islamic History	136	58	42.65%	78	57.35%
Management	230	72	31.30%	158	68.70%
Bangla	101	57	56.44%	44	43.56%
	929	470	50.59%	459	49.41%

(c) 3rd YEAR Hon's (Session-2012-13)

subject	Total	Present	(%)	Absent	(%)
Islamic History	134	52	38.81%	82	61.19%
Bangle	115	65	56.52%	50	43.48%
Political science	180	102	56.67%	78	43.33%
Physics	22	18	81.82%	04	18.18%
History	108	30	27.78%	78	72.22%
Philosophy	101	61	60.40%	40	39.60%
Management	180	15	8.33%	165	91.67%
	880	343	38.98%	537	61.02%

(d) 4th YEAR Hon's (Session-2013-14)

subject	Total	Present	(%)	Absent	(%)
Bangla	128	48	37.50%	80	62.50%
Management	142	25	17.61%	117	82.39%
Philosophy	102	59	57.84%	43	42.16%
Islamic History	102	27	26.47%	75	73.53%
Physics	18	16	88.89%	02	11.11%
Political science	171	110	64.33%	61	35.67%
History	104	56	53.85%	48	46.15%
	767	341	44.46%	426	55.54%

(e) M.A. Final Year, (Session-2014-15)

subject	Total	Present	(%)	Absent	(%)
Management	209	102	48.80%	107	51.20%
Islamic History	177	20	11.30%	157	88.70%
Philosophy	141	61	43.26%	80	56.74%
Bangla	148	18	12.16%	130	87.84%
Physics	16	10	62.5%	06	37.5%
Political science	320	120	37.5%	200	62.5%
History	118	48	40.68%	70	59.32%
	1129	379	33.57%	750	66.43%

(f) 1st Year-M.A. Final Year (Session 2010-11 to 2014-15)

	Total	Present	(%)	Absent	(%)
1st Year	1084	654	60.33%	430	39.66%
2nd Year	929	470	50.59%	431	46.39%
3rd Year	880	343	38.98%	537	61.02%
4th Year	767	341	44.46%	426	55.54%
M.A./ Final	1129	379	33.57%	750	66.43%

4.2 Discussions

To collect data on student absenteeism in tertiary education, Sirajganj govt. college was selected and four categories of respondents – Principal, Teachers, students and guardians were interviewed. Questionnaires were distributed among the respondents. They made their written comments where necessary. They also gave their opinions about the causes of student absenteeism. The findings about the causes of student absenteeism were collected from the four categories.

Socio-economic crisis: A large number of students coming from villages suffer from various

types of economic crises such as poverty, residence, distance from home to college, transportation, no support from in-laws house, disturbed by perverts on the way, lack of good communication, involvement with politics, physical illness, food etc. As their parents fail to provide the necessary money for their tuition fees and other expenses related to their education. They often get involved in private tuition as well as in some temporary jobs available nearby. That is why, they are compelled to remain absent from their classes.

Accommodation crisis in the educational institution: Not only Sirajganj govt. college, almost all educational institutions cannot afford to provide proper accommodation for students. The classrooms the educational institutions possess are not enough for the increasing number of students. So the students lose their interest in attending their classes.

Lacking proper implementation of attendance in Educational institutions: The students who do not attend their classes regularly are not punished at all by the departments they belong to as well as the authority for their absence. They are given pass marks both in course, term paper and voce examinations. So they do not think their presence in the classroom is necessary. Besides, the teachers show sympathy towards the students in all their examinations including tests, viva voce and term papers and lack of accountability both from the teachers and students.

Broad and complicated syllabus: The learners who get admitted into the colleges under the national university are comparatively of low calibre. Those (maximum students) who fail to get admitted into public universities and those who obtain lower marks come here. However, the syllabus prescribed for them is so broad and complicated that it often goes beyond their capability. So they remain busy only taking help from their private tutors to pass the examination. Besides, avoiding the classroom and textbooks, they get involved in collecting notes and reading cheap guidebooks.

Factors influencing dissatisfactory results in tertiary education

In response to the question about the dissatisfactory results of the students, all the respondent principal, teachers, students and guardians have pointed out that absenteeism has been the number one cause of dissatisfactory results in tertiary education. Depending on cheap notes and memorization without understanding are also the root of the poor performance of the students in the examination. This particular observation is unanimously agreed by the respondents.

Measures to be taken to ensure maximum presence of the students

According to the Principal and teachers of Sirajganj Govt. In college, the maximum presence of the students in the classroom can be ensured by taking some effective measures. They mentioned that regular roll calls, conduction of regular tutorial examinations and counselling of students can reduce student absenteeism. They also opined that show cause notice sent both to the students and to the guardian would stop absenteeism. At the same time, rewards for regular students and exercise for regular co-curricular activities would certainly encourage the students who will always feel the urge to attend classes regularly. The Principal will ensure a clean hygienic and lively classroom for the students. Teachers should adopt attractive methods of teaching, that is, question-answer method, discussion method and participatory method should be adopted.

Depending on private tuition and cheap guidebooks and hand notes handicap students' intellectual development and encourage them to become absentees. Private tuition and depending on guidebooks should be controlled.

5. Recommendations

Tertiary education plays a very important role in the development of the country. The future of the country depends on the success of students who secure tertiary education. However, absenteeism in tertiary education students is in the way of the development of the country. To stop absenteeism in tertiary education, the following recommendations have been made from the study:

Classroom and residence accommodation: To ensure the attendance of the students, the government should take proper initiatives to enhance the infrastructural capacity of all educational institutions immediately.

Syllabus: Syllabus should be shortened as well as suitable, modern and up to the mark for the learners. So that they can give their concentration to their textbook.

Recruitment of more teachers: For the huge number of students, more teachers should be recruited and proper training should be provided for them so that they can implement modern equipment in their classroom to draw the attention of the students. Filling up the vacant teachers' posts on a priority basis and making the teacher-student ratio 1:50.

Proper Implementation of Law and Regulations: The authority should be strict in implementing the laws and regulations so that the learners remaining absent from their classes do not get any illegal facilities.

Controlling guidebooks and private tuition: By controlling guidebooks and private tuition, we can bring the students back into the classroom.

6. Conclusions

Student absenteeism has been identified as a great problem in tertiary education not only in Sirajganj Govt. College but also in other colleges in Bangladesh. Absenteeism which hampers the overall intellectual development of the students. It also leads to poor results for the students. Some significant findings from the study were identified for the causes of absenteeism in tertiary education. Poverty, teachers showing sympathy towards the students in all their examinations, distance from home to college, lack of accommodation, involvement of politics, depending on private tuition and cheap guidebooks are the root causes of absenteeism according to the opinions of all respondents—Principal, teachers, students and guardians. The respondents also opined that the possible solutions are counselling the students, transportation facilities for the students, deterring irregular students from appearing at the examination, rewarding regular, poor and meritorious students, making classroom teaching attractive, banning notes and guide books

etc. The development of Bangladesh depends on the development of efficient human resources. It is only possible through the implementation of true education. To make our country prosperous, student absenteeism should be eradicated from tertiary educational institutions.

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